

QUIZ**LAST NAME: AKIBU****FIRST NAME: YINKA****PROGRAM CODE: PHGH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes).

The author did not use Zotero to insert references.

The author used the following software: MSOffice ProPlus

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

- 1. WHO style of writing uses non-discriminatory language. All of the listed guidelines below are correct except one.**
 - WHO's Health information can use stereotype language for intellectual impairment, if right.¹**
 - WHO's information must address all people equally.
 - WHO's information must address all people fairly.
 - WHO's information must not demean people based on sex or ethnicity.
- 2. All of the following are classic examples of stereotypes not allowed in WHO style of writing except one.**

¹ World Health Organization. *WHO Style Guide*. Geneva, Switzerland: (World Health Organization, 2004), 55.

- Older people are incapable, frail, and a burden to society.
 - Young people are rebellious, inexperienced, and always immature.
 - Nigeria and Ghana are examples of developing countries.²**
 - Nigeria and Ghana are examples of underdeveloped countries.
3. **Based on the WHO style of writing, the following are examples of the advantages of using a house style of writing except one.**
- House style ensures consistency of writing in a publication.
 - House style contributes to the corporate image of the organization.
 - House style streamlines and increases the efficiency of the writing and editing process.
 - The use of house style leads to a reduction in the production cost of the book.³**
4. **All the following are valid considerations when considering a research topic except one.**
- The potential audience and ethical considerations.
 - The supervisor's interest must supersede the student's interest.⁴**
 - Personal and professional goals.
 - The intellectual value and worth of the study.

² WHO, *WHO Style Guide*, 58.

³ WHO, *WHO Style Guide*, 1.

⁴ Bloomberg Linda and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. (Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications, 2008), 7.

5. **The following are valid examples of primary qualitative traditional methods except one.**
- Grounded Theory and Case Studies.
 - Ethnography and Narrative Inquiry/Biography.
 - Pharmacovigilance and Ungrounded method.⁵**
 - Phenomenology and Hermeneutics.
6. **Academic dishonesty and plagiarism have serious consequences. The following are valid examples of plagiarism except one.**
- The use of another writer's words with proper citation.⁶**
 - The use of another writer's words without proper citation.
 - The use of exact words of a source without quotation marks or indentation.
 - Falsifying Data.
7. **The following are helpful nuggets in the preparation of a literature review except one.**
- Ensuring the literature review is comprehensive.
 - Ensuring the review covers the major points of each topic.
 - Ensuring the argument is not necessarily following a logical flow.⁷**

⁵ Linda and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation*, 11.

⁶ Linda and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation*, 24.

⁷Turabian Kate, *Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, Eighth Edition. (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2013), 63.

- Ensuring the inclusion of the current and historical coverage of the topic.
8. **A researcher is required to communicate data ethically and to choose the most effective and appropriate graphics. The following statements are correct except one.**
- Tables are used to emphasize specific values.
- Tables are used to emphasize specific trends.⁸**
- Bar charts are used to emphasize comparison that can be seen as one.
- Line graphs are used to emphasize trends, usually over time.
9. **A research conclusion is usually built off and around the elements of a research introduction. The following are essential characteristics or purposes of a research conclusion except one.**
- Conclusions highlight a new significance.
- Conclusions suggest further research.
- Conclusion points out a practical application.
- Conclusion outlines the methodological procedures employed.⁹**
10. **The last big task of a researcher is to ensure that the research sentences are clear as much as the ideas allow. The following statements are helpful nuggets for improving the quality of a sentence except one.**

⁸ Kate, *Manual for Writers of Research Papers*,55.

⁹ Kate, *Manual for Writers of Research Papers*,73.

- The use of more passive words than active words in the dissertation.**¹⁰
- Avoidance of long introductory phrases and clauses.
- Putting key actions in verbs and not nouns.
- Putting new information at the end and familiar information to readers at the beginning of a sentence.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Bloomberg, Linda D., and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications, 2008.
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¹⁰Kate, *Manual for Writers of Research Papers*,74.